

SiEU Green
Sino-European innovative green
and smart cities

Sino-European Innovative Green and Smart Cities

Deliverable 6.1

Dissemination Plan

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Due date: 30/06/2018
Version: 2.0

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

Co-funded by the Chinese Ministry
of Science and Technology

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research, and Innovation Programme, under grant Agreement N° 774233

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme of the European Union

Co-funded by the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology

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SiEUGreen

The project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research, and Innovation programme, under grant Agreement N 774233 and from the Chinese Ministry of Science and Technology.

Throughout SiEUGreen's implementation, EU and China will share technologies and experiences, thus contributing to the future developments of urban agriculture and urban resilience in both continents.

The project SiEUGreen aspires to enhance the EU-China cooperation in promoting urban agriculture for food security, resource efficiency and smart, resilient cities.

The project contributes to the preparation, deployment and evaluation of showcases in 5 selected European and Chinese urban and peri-urban areas: a previous hospital site in Norway, community gardens in Denmark, previously unused municipal areas with dense refugee population in Turkey, big urban community farms in Beijing and new green urban development in Changsha Central China.

A sustainable business model allowing SiEUGreen to live beyond the project period is planned by joining forces of private investors, governmental policy makers, communities of citizens, academia and technology providers.

SiEUGreen
Sino-European innovative green
and smart cities

 facebook.com/SiEUGreen2020

 twitter.com/SiEUGreen

 linkedin.com/groups/8652505

Technical References

Project Acronym:	SiEUGreen
Project Title:	Sino-European Innovative Green and Smart Cities
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Project Duration:	January 2018 - December 2021

Deliverable N°:	D6.1 Dissemination Plan
Dissemination level ¹:	PU
Work Package:	WP 6 - Communication and Dissemination
Task:	T 6.1 Dissemination plan, tools and activities
Lead partner:	6 - EMETRIS
Contributing partner(-s):	1 - NMBU, 2 - NIBIO, 3 - CAAS, 4 - CREVIS, 5 - NORDREGIO, 8 - VILABS, 9 - OKYS LTD, 13 - Hatay, 14 - CASS, 15 - Sampas, 18 - IGZ, 19 - Photon
Due date of deliverable:	30/06/2018
Actual submission date:	29/06/2018

¹ **PU** = Public

PP = Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)

RE = Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)

CO = Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)

Document History			
Version	Date	Author - Partner	Summary of Changes
0.1	26/03/2018	6-EMETRIS	Outline Proposal
0.2	05/06/2018	6-EMETRIS	Style of Deliverable
1.0	27/06/2018	6-EMETRIS	Initial Draft for Peer Review
2.0	29/06/2018	6-EMETRIS	Final deliverable for the EC

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Executive Summary

The present Dissemination and Communication Plan (DaCP) introduces the SiEUGreen project dissemination and communication strategy and its implementation plan to be used by the consortium to ensure the **high visibility, accessibility and promotion of the project and its results during the whole Implementation grant period**. The current DaCP will also be a **reference context for evaluating the impact of communication and dissemination activities and will be annually updated as the project progresses**.

To achieve the maximum possible impact of its activities and support and strengthen EU-China collaboration, SiEUGreen will emphasize on **maximizing the effectiveness and space of its dissemination and communication activities**. These specific activities will not only **address the general public to raise awareness on the project** since it is one of the main target groups (citizens), but also **targets key stakeholders having a relevant role in the area of SiEUGreen Vision, Goals and Actions, undertaken by the project**.

The SiEUGreen project DaCP has been organized in various sections presenting the overall strategy, the objectives, the stakeholders, target groups and audiences, as well as the messages and all implementation activities.

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List of Abbreviations

CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)
D	Deliverable
DaCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
LP	Lead Partner
M	Number of month since the start project
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including the Commission Services)
PU	Public
R&D	Research and Development
R&I	Research and Innovation
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)
RRI	Responsible research and innovation
RTOs	Research and Technology Organizations
SMEs	Small and Medium Enterprises
STI	Science Technology and Innovation
T	Task
UA	Urban Agriculture
WP	Work Package

Introduction

The ultimate **success of SiEUGreen project** is strongly dependent on well-coordinated **dissemination and exploitation activities**. SiEUGreen Work Package 6 (WP6) **is devoted to dissemination and communication activities**.

Taking into consideration **challenges** and **opportunities** presented by global urbanization, the SiEUGreen project brings together a multi-disciplinary Consortium of European and Chinese researchers, technology providers, SMEs, financiers, local and regional authorities and resident communities, in order to apply **novel urban agricultural technological techniques new approaches** for **social engagement** and investigate the economic, environmental and social benefits of Urban Agriculture (UA). Consequently it has to convince all relevant parties to play an active role in the project. These notions guide the communication and dissemination activities in SiEUGreen. The WP6 should:

- Raise general **awareness** about the **project and its output** and **getting the necessary feedback**;
- **Building understanding and facilitating adoption of project results by the different stakeholder groups** that can directly benefit from the project;
- **Inform stakeholders** about the achievements of the project;
- **Aim for high transparency** and **accessibility** of the project output &
- **Try to monitor** and **evaluate** interest in the project.

The plan for Communication and Dissemination will identify and analyze the **project target audiences** and **define the most appropriate means/ tools for reaching the dissemination objectives**. The Plan:

- **Schedules activities**;
- **Defines the complementarity** of the activities &
- **Defines measures to assess** the impact of the **dissemination activities**.

In order to **ensure proper dissemination of the generated knowledge**, with regards to confidentiality, publication, and use of the knowledge.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan, also, identify **potential synergies** in order to enhance the dissemination range and impact.

It should be underlined that the dissemination plan will take into account the **special needs and peculiarities of every target group** and will design and implement suitable strategies and

utilize suitable tools. Apart from the active communities which are the main target audience of the SiEUGreen, an **outreach plan for other stakeholders** such as regulators, policy makers and the media will be also developed as part of the wider project's dissemination plan.

The implementation of this WP includes **several dissemination activities**, e.g. participation in relevant events and conferences, organization of project conferences, press releases, articles in popular newspapers, website, videos and social media dissemination activities, as well as the production of all the promotional material required for the online communication activities and the awareness raising campaigns (offline). All these can be classified in the **following categories of dissemination activities**:

- Flyers and brochures;
- Website and social networking;
- Conferences, meetings, workshops and presentations &
- Scientific articles and working-papers.

The Communication and Dissemination Plan will be **updated annually**, including the assessment of dissemination activities, in terms of impact and effectiveness.

Dissemination & Communication Strategy

Objectives

Dissemination and communication activities will support all Work Packages (WPs) ensuring mainly maximum visibility, scalability, and impact of the project activities. **Tailored dissemination activities** will be designed to make the project outcomes visible and accessible to the different target stakeholders, in order to enhance adoption and use.

The **objectives of the dissemination activities** will be to:

- **Promote** - Make sure different target audiences are Informed and educated;
- **Inform** - Make the outcomes (mainly the **models** and results) developed through the SiEUGreen project available to the different target audiences;
- **Engage** - Receive inputs and feedbacks from the various target groups;
- **Exploit** - Enhance SiEUGreen results exploitation potential;
- **Make sustainable** - Ensure that the outputs will be sustained after the end of the project lifetime &
- **Scale up** – Make sure potential users can use the results and models in order to scale them up.

Communication activities will complement the dissemination activities towards increasing the outreach of the project's results. The **objectives of the communication activities** will be to:

- **Reach out** - Show the impact and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities to the society;
- **Inform and promote** - Information about the project and its results will be publically available &
- **Multiple** - Audiences beyond the project's own community will be reached, including media and the broad public.

The objectives of the dissemination and communication activities will be **deployed in stages** during the project lifetime. In addition to the objectives specified above, other objectives will be targeted in these stages as follows:

Months	Objectives	Indicative Dissemination Channels
M 1-24	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disseminate project activities Enhance target group engagement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Project website & blog Social media Information material Contact with target groups Participation in third party events
M 25-48	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Disseminate project results Increase target group engagement & participation Network with other projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participation in networking Social media campaigns Scientific conferences, publications Project website Direct contacts

Dissemination and communication actions of the SiEUGreen project will be basically aligned to the **exploitation of the project’s results**. Efficient publicity and wide exposure of project’s results, tools, models and achievements will increase stakeholders’ engagement with the SiEUGreen project, and beyond the end of it. Ultimately, communication and dissemination activities will maximize SiEUGreen impact on **prompting dialogues, cooperation, coordination and establishing connections between EU and China stakeholders**.

The communication actions will accompany the R&I work of the project throughout its duration, while activities related to the dissemination and exploitation of results often continue even after the project has ended.

The main elements of dissemination and communication strategy of the SiEUGreen project can be described by using the theory of Five Ws and they are summarized in the figure bellow.

The plan for dissemination and communication will set questions that their answers are considered to gather all relevant information needed, defining the optimal and relevant interactions among:

Figure 1: The 5Ws of SiEUGreen Dissemination & Communication Strategy

Communication, dissemination and exploitation measures should be understood as “horizontal issues” that run alongside and complement research activities throughout the project’s life cycle, with the main goal to maximize the expected impact of the Project.

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Dissemination actors

Emetris-6 as WP6 leader will follow up the leadership of the project dissemination activities following the dissemination strategy. Emetris-6 will:

- (i) Install the most suitable tools for maximum visibility and impact;
- (ii) Ensure that all partners contribute to dissemination activities &
- (iii) Assess the dissemination results.

Annex I presents in more detail each partner's tasks and responsibilities for dissemination activities.

Dissemination target groups/ audiences

During the **proposal submission**, SiEUGreen project has organized its dissemination activities in a way that the maximum positive result is gained. In order to gain the best outcome it is decided to focus its promotion and raise awareness, at first priority, to **3 specific audiences**. The aim is to disseminate and communicate the project idea, scope and results and this way to involve them in UA processes. The target audiences of the SiEUGreen project are:

Table 1: Target audiences of the SiEUGreen project on Submission

Public administration institutions	Residents	Companies
As multipliers for increasing residents' participation, as well as the policy level, for further support the promotion of such practices.	As immediate and long term beneficiaries; distinct groups: A. Long term unemployed; B. Elders; C. Vulnerable citizens group & D. General audience.	As third parties that will design, aggregate, produce and deliver resource-efficient UA services, tools and technologies

Nevertheless, during the discussions made so far, partnerships has decided to **broader** the above mentioned target audiences to the **following 6 main groups** of groups, audiences, stakeholders possible to be interested by the project outputs and therefore dissemination activities must target them:

Table 2: Target audiences of the SiEUGreen project on Implementation (Interested Groups)

1. Citizens	Citizens (home owners or in rent) in Europe, China and around the world are the main target group in disseminating since they can participate themselves and push authorities, as active society members. <i>E.g. Residents are immediate and long term beneficiaries; Activities include: balcony, wall and rooftop farming.</i>
2. Civil society - any form of collaborative action	Groups of people, networks, clusters, activists and any form of existing or potential form of collaboration and participation.

<p>3. EU & Chinese Policy-makers & Funding agencies</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – The European Commission; – Public Authorities at national, regional and local level; – Funding and Regulatory bodies; – Think Tanks; – Innovation Transfer Organizations; – Professional Associations & – Local, Regional authorities and other stakeholders, through the operation of community gardens, communal meet ups and the provision of a local support network. <p><i>Public authorities are multipliers for increasing residents' participation, as well as the policy level, for further support the promotion of such practices.</i></p>
<p>4. Chinese & Europeans Research communities</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Research Institutes; – Independent researchers; – Students and universities & – Other Research and Technology Organizations (RTOs) and Higher Education Institutes.
<p>5. Market Stakeholders</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – EU and Chinese companies (SMEs in particular); – EU and Chinese Clusters; – Private Corporations; – Real Estate Developers, Architects, Engineers; – Innovation Agencies & – Companies, <i>SMEs as third parties that will design, aggregate, produce and deliver resource-efficient UA services, tools and technologies.</i>
<p>6. Related EU & Chinese initiatives</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – H2020 and other programs & – Bilateral Initiatives.

Their roles are defined in the table below:

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Table 3: Role of SiEUGreen dissemination target audiences

Roles	1. Citizens	2. Civil society - any form of collaborative action	3. EU & Chinese Policy-makers & Funding agencies	4. Chinese & Europeans Research communities	5. Market Stakeholders	6. Related EU & Chinese initiatives
Give feedback on project activities and results	X	X		X	X	
Bring inputs on research findings, existing tools and best practices				X	X	X
Help actively support EU-China policy dialogues and their visibility	X			X	X	X
Enhance project's visibility				X	X	X
Help foster EU-China cooperation on STI R&D				X	X	X
Consider project outputs for defining new upcoming rules governing EU-China STI R&D cooperation	X					X
Promote the project in their contact networks		X		X	X	X

Messages to be disseminated

SiEUGreen will produce a rich and diverse series of outputs, spanning from Research Papers to Innovation and Business Models. The following list summarizes the main outputs to be disseminated to the identified target groups during the project lifetime:

Table 4: Main Outputs To Be Disseminated

WP1	<p>Develop and secure institutional and social structures for resource-efficient and resilient cities with UA. The outcome focuses on developing a broader conceptual framework for the project:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Engagement of residents, the role of governance and institutional settings, land use issues, knowledge transfer and long-term resilient structures and inclusive communities.
WP2	<p>Based on selected key technologies, the output will verify and test out these technologies, to facilitate their use on the large scale showcases in order to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Provide an overview and selection of technologies to be demonstrated in the showcases; – Verify the feasibility and identify potential challenges involved in implementation of the technologies; – Facilitate successful implementation in the showcases & – Deliver the implementation plan and evaluation of the selected technologies to be demonstrated in the showcases.
WP3	<p>The functionalities of the previous WP will be tested and validated, in order to organize and implement the showcase deployment of SiEUGreen in China, Norway, Denmark, and Turkey. The outputs include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Recruit and engage communities & – Implement the awareness raising campaigns for reaching participation from various environments.
WP4	<p>Outputs supporting the EU and Chinese countries on the “know-how” transfer to be disseminated, as so to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Achieve a successful urban agricultural food production with zero waste, minimum transport, reuse, recycle and reduced environmental and energy burden to contribute to circular economy.
WP5	<p>To develop sustainable business model for the commercialization of the SiEUGreen solution and identifying potential investors and alternative sources of funding, outputs include:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Assessment of the economic, environmental, social and business benefits of the Showcases;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Assessment of the nature and characteristics of current and future market demand in EU and China for UA solutions; – Map the global competitive landscape, assess the state of competition and provide estimation of the Market Potential, both in EU and China, for UA solutions & – Development a commercialization strategy for the two geographical areas; – Assessment of the potential markets and needs of all distinct user groups in EU and China for the UA solutions.
WP6	<p>Developing and implementing a multi-dimensional communication and dissemination strategy to ensure the replication and sustainability of SIEUGreen project with the ultimate output:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – To increase awareness and participation among project stakeholders.

Dissemination Strategy, Tools and Channels

In order to successfully deliver the above messages to the respective target audiences and reach the highest impact possible, the project consortium will refer to a **Before-Between-After Strategy** since the core of the project is (rather small scale) deployment of the pilots in the specific areas – partners among the partnership. This is a suitable strategy due to the construction sites but can also be quite successful to convey the message across all target groups using visual forms and such easier and more powerful succeeding thus better results.

Together with the Before-Between-After Strategy, the following **threefold Strategy** will be followed, incorporating:

- (i) Online and interactive tools and channels;
- (ii) Non electronic tools and channels &
- (iii) Physical interactive tools and channels.

All material supports used to present the content of the project to a target audience is described as *Dissemination Tools*.

All mediums through which the project results are transmitted and relayed to the target audiences is described as *Dissemination Channels*.

Online dissemination and interaction

Using effectively **online presence** tools and techniques will provide the SiEUGreen Project with modern and efficient means to share project results and materials, exchanging feedback with every interested stakeholders.

Website

The **website** (D6.2) will be used by the project partners and will be created, sustained and upgraded by 9-OKYS to become as user-friendly and interactive as possible. It will be used as a repository of useful information and contacts for all stakeholders and target groups that participate, engage, or involve in the project strategy implementation. The website will give stakeholders public access to project resources and publications in addition to providing visitors with regular related news.

The website will be maintained beyond the end of the project in order to ensure the project's results sustainable dissemination and impact.

Action Plan

- M6 first draft including the specifications for website (9-OKYS);
- M10 the website of SiEUGreen Project will be live (9-OKYS);
- 9-OKYS will update the website with useful information and contacts for R&D communities and industry players, based on inputs from partners;
- Search Engine optimization (SEO) parameters and web statistics will be performed and analyzed to drive more visit to the website of SiEUGreen &
- The project website is maintained beyond the end of the project lifetime.

Non-electronic dissemination

Project public deliverables

A major communication of external dissemination is the creation of project deliverables. Over the entire project duration, the consortium will produce a wide range of official deliverables. All (*except for the deliverables of WP8 that involve the ethics requirements and are Confidential, only for members of the consortium*) will be made publicly available onto the project website, in order to spread the project excellence and disseminate knowledge, as widely as possible.

Action Plan

- Project deliverables are drafted using the Word template designed at the beginning of the project and are systematically shared through tramwork.com platform, until finalized and uploaded to the website of the project &
- The final compressed PDF version of all deliverables is planned to be systematically available to 9-OKYS so that it can be uploaded on the project website for general public to access.

Project publications

The overall goal regarding the project publications is to **favor open access to these scientific publications**, in order to enlarge the target audience. The project partners will endeavor to select those publishers and scientific journals that can assure such open access without restriction, taking into account the quality of the publisher and impact factor to enlarge the target audience. The partners will publish in peer-reviewed scientific publications and then self-archive a version of the article for free public use in their institutional repository, in a central repository, or on some other open access website. The project website will house a “SiEUGreen Channel” for open access to the peer-reviewed publications of the project.

Project publications may also include articles in topic-specific journals, magazines and newsletters.

Action Plan

- Over the project duration, project partners commit to release at least 10 publications;
- Before submitting a scientific publication, partners are invited to send a draft version to the consortium members According to article 29.1 of the

Grant Agreement Number 774233 of the European Commission “A beneficiary that intends to disseminate its results must give advance notice to the other beneficiaries of — unless agreed otherwise — at least 45 days, together with sufficient information on the results it will disseminate.”;

- According to the same article (29.1) “Any other beneficiary may object within — unless agreed otherwise — 30 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the dissemination may not take place unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard these legitimate interests”, taking into account to the article 29.2 stating that “Each beneficiary must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.”;
- All publication must be given to 9-OKYS into PDF format to make them available through the website of the project &
- All partners contribute to the promotion and dissemination of the various publications.

Physical interactive dissemination

Project's events

Project events will act as a bond to **highlight and promote the main outcomes of the project**, to the respective target audiences, enabling valuable **feedback** and providing fertile ground for **policy discussion** and **brainstorming**. At the same time, the project events will support stakeholders to take action and implement pilot type projects and business models.

Project events are including:

- Organization of Conferences (T4.3 LP 8-Vilabs & 6.4 LP 6-Emetris). The Conferences could be organized in combination with a project meeting that will host a University during that period.
- Organization of Workshops (T 3.2 LP 1-NMBU, T 3.3 LP 2-NIBIO, T 4.3 LP 8-Vilabs, T 5.4 LP 6-Emetris, T 6.4 LP 6-Emetris, T 6.1 LP 6-Emetris)

Action Plan

- Organization of events of internal the project &
- Make amendments, regarding budget allocation if needed.

Participation in external events

Through the participation in external events, the members of the consortium will have an opportunity to **facilitate knowledge sharing and personal interaction**. External events are a great channel to build communities with audiences both from the EU and China. All partners will contribute, proposing major events to participate. Indicatively, SiEUGreen could be promoted in trade fairs, exhibitions and scientific conferences.

The partners of SiEUGreen will use their participation in external events as an additional opportunity to **establish synergies with other initiatives having similar scope**, in order to avoid duplication of effort and save resources.

Action Plan

- Project partners contribute with input on interesting events they have identified;
- Project partners inform on possible relevant events that they will participate;
- On completion of each event, every partner will provide information on their actual participation in the event, in order to be specifically recorded &

- Details on previous paragraph should include the name of actual event, the dates of the event, where and when it took place, the name of the representatives who participated, approximate number of participants, the nature of the event, whether or not the participation was only for SiEUGreen Project, means used to promote the project, dissemination material used, aspects of the project that have been mainly promoted, number of participants per day visited the hosting booth or number of attendees and number of flyers, brochures etc. that have been distributed.

Important notice on data collection and protection

Regarding the contacts made on the occasion of external events, only their data can be used by the consortium in order to inform them about the project with their consent, using the Consent Form for External Events, available in Annex III, or using any other means (e.g. email).

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Disseminating: Using the right tools for the right audiences

The table below presents an overview of the tools and channels to be used by the SiEUGreen project in order to disseminate the information to the relevant dissemination target groups.

Table 5: Dissemination: Tools and Channels for Corresponding Audiences

Dissemination tools and channels	Main Target Groups				
	1. Citizens & Civil society	3. EU & Chinese Policy-makers & Funding agencies	4. Chinese & Europeans Research communities	5. Market Stakeholders	6. Related EU & Chinese initiatives
Project Documentation					
Project flyer	X		X	X	X
Project brochures	X		X	X	X
Project publications					
Press releases	X		X	X	X
Project newsletters	X		X	X	X
Project deliverables	X	X	X	X	X
Online presence					
Project website	X		X	X	X

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Related websites	X		X	X	X
Related Social Media (Twitter, Facebook, LinkedIn, YouTube etc.)	X		X	X	X
Events					
Project's events	X	X	X	X	X
External events	X	X	X	X	X

Expected Impact of the dissemination activities

SiEUGreen project brings together a multi-disciplinary Consortium of European and Chinese researchers, technology providers, SMEs, financiers, local and regional authorities and resident communities, in order to apply novel urban agricultural technological techniques new approaches for social engagement and investigate the economic, environmental and social benefits of urban agriculture, with an outreach far beyond the consortium membership.

A Key Performance Indicator (KPI) is a measurable value that demonstrates how effectively the project is achieving its key objectives. During the duration of the project, members of the consortium will monitor and collect data, reporting the on-going dissemination material. This information will be constantly examined in relation to the pre-set KPIs. The results of the process will verdict on the impact and the success of the dissemination process.

Table 6: Dissemination KPIs

Project website, Blog	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – At least 1.000 visits per year with duration at least 2 minutes for the 40% of the users.
Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Twitter Feed: A minimum of 10 tweets per month; – Videos: At least 2.000 views on YouTube and other channels; – Linkedin: A minimum of 10 monthly updates & – Facebook: A minimum of 10 monthly posts.
Brochures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – At least 1.000 brochures printed and delivered for each partner.
Publication	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Partners release at least 10 scientific publications that will be published in international journals and conferences.
Project events	<p>Organize at least:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> – 5 conferences – 10 seminars – 10 workshops – 10 presentations – 200+ attendants, at the final conference <p><i>(numbers refer to the total project)</i></p>

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Communication strategy and master plan

Objectives of the communication activities

In addition to the dissemination activities, the **communication activities** will guarantee the communication of the project as a whole, its objectives, its activities and the findings to all interested stakeholders. The principle objectives of the project include:

- **Support dissemination activities;**
- **Raise awareness for the project,** its objectives, its activities and the findings &
- **Share and promote the project's events,** in order to attract attention.

Lead partner, regarding the project communication activities, together with the dissemination strategy as described in the previous paragraph, is 6-Emetris. All partners, contributing to the current Work Package will contribute with their tasks and responsibilities on communication actions, something that is displayed graphically in the table below:

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<i>L = Lead Partner</i> <i>C = Contributor Partner</i>	1-NMBU	2-NIBIO	3-CAAS	4-CREVIS	5-NORDREGIO	6-EMETRIS	7-AAKS	8-VILABS	9-OKYS LTD	10-BAEISU	11-BGVS	12-AQUA	13-HATAY	14-CASS	15-SAMPAS	16-HHEPSTI	17-SEECON	18-IGZ	19-PHOTON
Logo of the Project & Visual Identity																			
Creation of the project logo	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Production of templates for deliverables, presentations etc.	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Printed Material																			
Production and distribution of the brochures-flyers of the project	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Videos																			
Creation of a promotional videos for the project	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Press Releases																			
Production of press releases	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Website																			
Create & manage the website of the project	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C
Social Media																			
Create & manage the social media pages for the project	C	C	C	C	C	L	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C	C

Communication tools and activities

In order to achieve the aforementioned communication objectives, a **variety of communication tools and activities** will be used as follows. It is important to note that the use of a tool or an activity can be used both for dissemination and communication purposes.

Logo of the Project & Visual Identity

Colors and shapes referring to Urban Agriculture, nature and circular economy will be used for the Logo of the project. Based on the color palette used for the logo, a set of templates will be designed and become available, including:

- A template for the deliverables of the project &
- A template for presentations, within the project.

Action Plan

- Emetris-6 will design a couple of suggestions for the logo of the project;
- On the kick-off meeting all partners will vote for the one of their preference;
- Emetris-6 will prepare all relevant templates of the project &
- Emetris-6 will have everything uploaded onto the platform used by all partners in the scope of the project and made them available to every single partner.

Printed Material

Except for the brochures, the printed material includes all the material that will be used in order to promote the project and could include, excluding the brochures posters of the project, project fact sheet etc., depending on the case of use. The general idea is to reach large audiences in a short period of time.

The brochures-flyers of the project will be produced to present the benefits and the impact of the project to the general public, with easy to read content. Brief information regarding the different technologies involved will be offered in the brochure and tasks in progress will be presented.

Action Plan

- Emetris-6 will design the project brochure-flyer;
- Partners will make comments on the given design;
- Emetris-6 will have everything uploaded onto the platform used by all partners in the scope of the project and made them available to every single partner;

- Any other updated/ other version will be available to all partners using the same procedures &
- By the end of the project, at least 1.000 copies of the brochures-flyers per partner will have been printed and distributed.

Website

The project website will be used both as the main dissemination tool, but at the same time as principle communication tool. It will be used as a gateway to share project information as widely as possible. The **website** will be used by the project partners and will be created, sustained and upgraded by 9-OKYS to become as user-friendly and interactive as possible. It will be used as a repository of useful information and contacts for all stakeholders and target groups that participate, engage, or involve in the project strategy implementation. The website will give stakeholders public access to project resources and publications in addition to providing visitors with regular related news.

The website will be maintained beyond the end of the project in order to ensure the project’s results sustainable dissemination and impact.

Action Plan

- On M6 first draft including the specifications for website (9-OKYS);
- On M10 the website of SiEUGreen Project will be live (9-OKYS);
- OKYS-9 will update the website with useful information and contacts for R&D communities and industry players, based on inputs from partners;
- Search Engine optimization (SEO) parameters and web statistics will be performed and analyzed to drive more visit to the website of SiEUGreen &
- The project website is maintained beyond the end of the project lifetime.

Social Media

Social media are considered to be a powerful marketing tool, highly interactive and well established all over the EU and China. With their use the focus is on the strengthening of the presence of the project in both continents. The project will include the following social media platforms:

- **Twitter:** An account will be created to inform briefly the broader community about the project;

- **YouTube:** An account will be created to communicate all relevant videos on the web, on users’ experiences; how startups gain a direct benefit from SIEUGREEN etc.
- **LinkedIn:** A LinkedIn Group will be created to facilitate conversations on interesting relevant topics, published by the members of the Group, focusing mainly on the experts.
- **Facebook:** A Facebook page will be created to serve as a platform for sharing, discussion and communication of the whole project.
- **Social Media in China:** The key thing in order to do understand how social media work in China is that almost all of the widely used “western social media” platforms like Facebook, YouTube, twitter and so on are banned in China. As a result the partnership will utilize alternative platforms available in China, with the most popular being Sina Weibo (*twitter*), Toudou Youku (*YouTube*) and WeChat (*All-in-on Social Media*).

Action Plan

- Emetris-6 will choose proper official names for all “western social media” platforms and make them available to other partners to confirm;
- Create accounts on all “western social media” platforms;
- Update and manage these profiles periodically &
- Find a Chinese contact to create, update and manage Social Media in China, both in English and Chinese in accordance to the EU ones.

Press Releases

Press releases will take place when and where there will be important news to communicate about the project and minimum one every year. The mass media will be used to consistently provide news with a project brief and official description widely disseminated to outside media outlets, to announce important news about the project.

Action Plan

- Emetris-6 will prepare press releases for the project when required for any important milestone of the project, to be published in the adequate means;
- Partners comment on the content of the press releases;
- Press releases take place &
- The relevant release is communicated through other channels (i.e. website, network of contacts and so on) in order to achieve maximum awareness.

Videos

Videos will be developed and be published and promoted in the channel of the project on YouTube, showcasing users experience and on how startups gain a direct benefit from SIEUGREEN. The before and after of the showcases of the project can be presented through short videos. These videos will be actively promoted through all projects online channels.

Action Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Partners create as many short videos as needed, including before and after of the showcases, best practices and event trailers during the project lifetime; – Emetris will post the videos onto the YouTube Channel of the project, as long as to all online platforms of the project for maximum visibility & – Partners will actively promote these videos through their respective channels.
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Expected Impact of the communication activities

As stated in the impact of the dissemination activities of the project, a series of KPIs are considered to monitor the impact and overall success of the communication processes of SiEUGreen project. These series of KPIs are detailed below.

Table 7: Communication KPIs

Project website, Blog	– At least 1.000 visits per year with duration at least 2 minutes for the 40% of the users.
Social Media	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> – Twitter Feed: A minimum of 10 tweets per month; – Videos: At least 2.000 views on YouTube and other channels; – LinkedIn: A minimum of 10 monthly updates & – Facebook: A minimum of 10 monthly posts.
Printed Material	– At least 1.000 brochures-flyers printed and delivered for each partner.
Videos	– At least 2.000 views on YouTube and other channels.
Press Releases	– At least 1 press release every 12 months.

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Annexes

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Annex I - Communication and Dissemination Activities List

The table below highlights the communication and dissemination activities; the responsible partner and the related Task/Deliverable as indicated in the Grant Agreement.

Due to discrepancies between deliverables, the contribution of relevant budgets and the contribution of the partners is drafted in the following table and will be finalized as soon as possible.

Table 8: Communication and Dissemination Activities List with the according budgets per partner

	EU Activity Categories	Partner responsible	Task/ Deliverable	Amount in €	Total Amount to be delivered	Details
1	Organization of a Conference	All, LP Vilabs	T 4.3	There is travel budget to all partners but no dedicated budget to organize a conference	1	A knowledge sharing conference which will be organised at the end of Year 3
		All, LP Emetris	T 6.4	There is travel budget to all partners but no dedicated budget to organize a conference	5	Identify possible dates, co-organizations in the dissemination stage, and budget (our conference KPI is 5) Attendants in the final conference: 200+
2	Organization of a Workshop				10 in total	
		All, LP NMBU	T 3.2	NMBU 5 workshops = 8.000€	5	Check whether they are considered Communication or Dissemination (our workshop KPI is 10)
		All, LP NIBIO	T 3.3	NIBIO Workshops with EU & Chinese stakeholders and dissemination of showcases in year 2 and 4 during the project period. Dissemination of European and Chinese experiences = 11.832€	2	Training workshops can be considered such
		All, LP Vilabs	T 4.3	NORDREGIO Organization of workshops and meeting in the three case-study areas in the Europe with 2 visits in each of the areas. = 7.000€	2	In the KPI list there are 5 conferences, 10 workshops, 10 seminars (probably training), 10 presentation (to various events) and 200+ attendants, at

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EU Activity Categories	Partner responsible	Task/Deliverable	Amount in €	Total Amount to be delivered	Details
	All, LP Emetris	T 5.4		2	Two scenario planning workshops where different possible future scenarios will be exploited. The final conference
	All, LP Emetris	T 6.4			Also Emetris has to organize learning workshops in the T 6.4 but that can also considered part of a conference-no budget
3	Press release	All, LP Emetris	T 6.1	No dedicated budget	At least 1 every 12 months Staff costs will be reported as dissemination or communication costs
4	Non-scientific and non-peer-reviewed publication (popularized publication)				<i>All partners, please, do specify if such activities are planned</i>
5	Exhibition				<i>No such activity planned</i>
6	Brochures and Flyers	All, LP Emetris	D 6.3		<p>NMBU Printing and design of promotional materials (2.000 brochures, 200 posters etc) = 5.000€</p> <p>CREVIS Printing and design of promotional materials (2.000 brochures, 200 posters etc) = 5.000€</p> <p>NORDREGIO Printing and design of promotional materials (brochures, posters, websites, etc): = 3.000 €</p> <p>Emetris Design of dissemination material = 4.000€</p> <p>AAKS Printing and design of promotional materials (2.000 brochures, 200 posters etc) = 3.000 €</p> <p>VILAB Printing and design of promotional materials (2.000 brochures, 200 posters etc) = 4.350 €</p> <p>1.000 brochures for each partner</p> <p>Number of brochures printed and delivered - Our KPI is 1.000 brochures for each partner, Actively deliver project's brochures to stakeholders and the public exploiting partners' network</p>

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EU Activity Categories		Partner responsible	Task/ Deliverable	Amount in €	Total Amount to be delivered	Details
				OKYS Printing and design of promotional materials (2.000 brochures, 200 posters etc) = 4.000 € Hatay Printing and design of promotional materials (1.500 brochures, 200 posters etc) = 1.903 € Seecon Printing and design of promotional materials (2.000 brochures, 200 posters etc) = 2.000 €		
7	Training	All, LP NIBIO	T 4.1	No specific budget	-	Can be part of the workshops
		Emetris	T 6.3			
8	Social Media	All , LP Emetris (+ a Chinese partner to be identified)	T 6.1	Staff Cost	10 per month	Twitter
		All , LP Emetris (+ a Chinese partner to be identified)	T 6.1		10 per month	LinkedIn
		All , LP Emetris (+ a Chinese partner to be identified)	T 6.1		10 per month	Facebook

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EU Activity Categories		Partner responsible	Task/ Deliverable	Amount in €	Total Amount to be delivered	Details
		All , LP Emetris (+ a Chinese partner to be identified)	T 6.1			Chinese Social Media
9	Website	LP OKYS	D 6.2	Staff	1.000 Yearly visits	Link with app and communication and dissemination tool
					Duration of visits more than 2 min. for 40% of users	
10	Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)					<i>No such activity planned</i>
11	Participation to a Conference	All, LP Emetris	T 6.1	There is travel budget to all partners in order to participate in conferences and external events	5	Participation in relevant events and conferences
		All, LP Emetris	T 6.4	There is travel budget to all partners in order to participate in conferences and external events	5	Participation in relevant events and conferences
12	Participation to a Workshop					<i>Not well defined. All partners, please, do specify if such activities are planned</i>
13	Participation to an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop					<i>Not well defined. All partners, please, do specify if such activities are planned</i>

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	EU Activity Categories	Partner responsible	Task/ Deliverable	Amount in €	Total Amount to be delivered	Details
14	Video/ Film	LP Emetris	T 6.3		10 short videos	Youtube, 2.000 total views on YouTube and other channels
15	Brokerage Event					<i>No such activity planned</i>
16	Pitch Event					<i>No such activity planned</i>
17	Trade Fair					<i>No such activity planned</i>
18	Participation in activities organized jointly with other H2020 projects					<i>Could be the case. All partners, please, do specify if such activities are planned</i>
19	Scientific Papers	All			10	<i>Not listed in the EU list</i> (Not considered communication or dissemination but there are in the KPIs). Scientific papers will be published in international journals and conferences

Annex II - Social Media Strategy Plan

Strategy overview

The strategy plan describes the actions and efforts of 6-Emetris and other partners in order to implement all actions described on T6.1 of the project. In the following paragraphs the current situation and the overall strategy overview for both dissemination and communication of the project activities is being described and it will be annually updated.

The role of Emetris

Emetris is the administrator of all Social Media, while other partners contribute significantly on the content production. Metric tools are being used (e.g. twitter analytics on the twitter platform) in order to measure the presence and overall performance on the social media.

Social media specifications and objectives

The platforms utilized by the project have been already described in the body of the current deliverable.

Table 9: Social Media Terminology (Source: European Commission, Directorate-General for Research & Innovation H2020 Programme, Guidance Social media guide for EU funded R&I projects, Version 1.0, 6 April 2018)

Hashtag #

Hashtag is added in front of any word or phrase in a post, this makes it easier for users to locate specific content or themes

Examples: #UrbanAgriculture, #CircularEconomy, #H2020

How it works?

Hashtagging always starts with the # symbol, followed by a specific string of alphanumeric characters, usually a word or unspaced phrase. The hashtag may contain letters, digits, and underscores.

Using a hashtag makes the keyword or phrase in the post searchable. It is like a label that clusters and links similar content, the same way keywords do when scientific papers are published.

Why hashtags?

- # To increase outreach;
- # To capitalize on existing trends;

- # To consolidate and group content &
- # To encourage interaction.

Handle @

The Handle defines a unique user name mainly used to identify a person or a project's account.

Examples: @EU_Commission for the European Commission's Twitter official page

How it works?

Linkage with a specific account always starts with the @ symbol, followed by a name or phrase to identify the account.

Why handles?

- @ To link to someone else's account (*known as a 'mention'*) by using their handle elsewhere in a post. This will link the certain post to the mentioned user's account &
- @ To send a direct reply to someone, by starting a message with their handle.

The characteristics of every social media platform to be used are described in the following paragraphs.

LinkedIn

LinkedIn is the primary social media platform utilized by SiEUGreen, acting as an interactive communication channel with different stakeholders both in Europe and China. On the 31st of January 2018, a private group page has been created, under the name SiEUGreen (<https://www.linkedin.com/groups/8652505>). The group accepts new members only after approval by the administrators. On the 27th of June 2018 the group counts 62 conversations over its 54 members of diverse profiles and ethnicity. The overall objective is to control and encourage the publication to a minimum of 10 monthly updates per month.

Table 10: LinkedIn Directions for Posting

What can be posted?

Text (no character limit), photos, GIFs, videos, links, etc.

The SiEUGreen Group on LinkedIn

- All project partners (not only the administrator of the page, 6-Emetris) can post relevant material into the group 'Conversations', such as articles, pictures, publications and so on;
- All project partners (not only the administrator of the page, 6-Emetris) can establish connections with already established groups of the platform. After having identified a relevant account they should inform the administrator to establish connection &

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- The partners that already have a strong, well established LinkedIn presence, should communicate the information that is shared on the account of SiEUGreen, in order to reach already existing audiences.

Sample LinkedIn pages

- HORIZON 2020 Framework Programme for Research and Innovation
- H2020 MARIE CURIE Actions Fellowship & Research Grants, PhD Careers and R&D Jobs
- INEA - Innovation and Networks Executive Agency
- EASME - EU projects & partner search
- EASME - Environment projects & partner search
- BBI JU - Bio-based Industries Joint Undertaking

Figure 2: Private group page of the project on LinkedIn

Twitter

Twitter is used mainly to communicate and interact with the European community, as it is blocked in mainland China. On the 31st of January a twitter page has been created, under the name SiEUGreen and the user name @sieugreen (<https://twitter.com/sieugreen>). On the 27th

of June 2018 the twitter account counts 66 tweets and 9 followers. The overall objective is to control and encourage the publication of monthly tweets to a minimum of 10 monthly updates per month.

Figure 3: SiEUGreen twitter, earned 2.2K impressions over this 28 day period (source twitter.com)

The latest impact performance (as measured by twitter analytics), describing the number of times users saw the tweet on twitter the last 28 days (current date being the 27th of June 2018), is presented in the figure above, having earned 2.2K impressions over this 28 day period.

Table 11: Twitter Directions for Posting

What can be posted?

Text of up to 280 characters. This excludes media attachments (photos, images, videos, etc.) and quoted tweets (displaying someone else's tweet within the original one) but includes links (a URL is always altered to 23 characters).

The @sieugreen Account on twitter

- Only the administrator of the page (6-Emetris) can post on the twitter account;
- All other partners should use the handle @sieugreen to link to the account of the project;
- Another alternative for the project partners that should be used combined with the previous one, is the hashtag #SiEUGreen to cluster all relevant posts;
- The partners that already have a strong, well established twitter presence, should communicate the information that is shared on the account of SiEUGreen, in order to reach already existing audiences;
- Some relevant tweets can include handles, such as @EU_H2020 to maximize the visibility and to be recognized as part of the H2020 community;
- Twitter is becoming increasingly visual – the posts should include pictures, videos, GIFs or data visualizations to spark interest;
- During many occasions, such as during project meetings, pictures should be taken and posted, tagging other twitter accounts (*up to 10*), to build a relationship with a specific audience and make them aware of content that might interests them (the account tagged receives a notification) &
- Make use of twitter analytics to track the performance of the account.

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Relevant twitter handles

@EU_H2020, @MSCActions, @Mariecurie_alum, @mariescurie_ire, @TNavracsicsEU, @Net4Mobility, @FET_eu, @EU_Growth, @EUHomeAffairs, @EU_TrustSec, @OpenAccessEC, @DG_Connect, @DigitalAgendaEU, @EU_Agri, @EUClimateAction, @Energy4Europe, @INEA_EU, @EU_ENV, @EU_MARE, @Transport_EU, @ERC_Research, @EU_EASME, @IMI_JU, @cleansky_ju, @fch_ju, @BBI2020, @ECSEL_JU, @Shift2Rail_JU, @SESAR_JU

Relevant twitter hashtags

#H2020, #MSCA, #MarieCurious, #MSCAjobalert, #MSCA20, #EUBudget4results, #Bioeconomy, #EIPagri, #ePrivacy, #cybersecurity, #SecurityUnion, #openaccess, #DSMeu

Figure 4: Page of SiEUGreen on twitter

Facebook

Another very popular social media and social networking service in the EU is facebook. Facebook is used mainly to communicate and interact with the European community, as it is blocked in mainland China, just like twitter. On the 31st of January a facebook page has been created, under the name SiEUGreen and the user name @SiEUGreen2020 (<https://www.facebook.com/SiEUGreen2020/>). On the 27th of June 2018 the facebook account counts 60 posts, 29 page likes and 31 page followers. The overall objective is to

control and encourage the publication of monthly posts to a minimum of 10 monthly updates per month.

Table 12: Facebook Directions for Posting

What can you post?

Text (no character limit), photos, GIFs, videos, links, etc.

The @SiEUGreen2020 Account on Facebook

- Only the administrator of the page (6-Emetris) can post on the facebook account;
- All other partners should either use the handle @ SiEUGreen2020 to link to the account of the project or post something on the relevant facebook ‘visitor’s posts’ section (although it is kind of hide in the page of the project);
- Another alternative for the project partners that should be used combined with the previous ones, is the hashtag #SiEUGreen to cluster all relevant posts;
- The partners that already have a strong, well established facebook presence, should communicate the information that is shared on the account of SiEUGreen, in order to reach already existing audiences;
- Some relevant posts can include handles, such as @EuropeanCommission to maximize the visibility and to be recognized as part of the European community;
- Facebook is becoming increasingly visual – the posts should include pictures, videos, GIFs or data visualizations to spark interest &
- During many occasions, such as during project meetings, pictures should be taken and posted, tagging other facebook accounts and/ or users, to build a relationship with a specific audience and make them aware of content that might interests them (the account tagged receives a notification).
- Make use of facebook analytics to track the performance of the account.

Sample facebook pages

- <https://www.facebook.com/Marie.Curie.Actions>
- <https://www.facebook.com/FET.europe>
- <https://www.facebook.com/DigitalSingleMarket>
- <https://www.facebook.com/pages/EGov-Infso>
- <https://www.facebook.com/EUScienceInnov>
- <https://www.facebook.com/EU.Growth>
- <https://www.facebook.com/EUAgri>

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Figure 5: Page of SiEU Green on facebook

Videos

For the development and sharing of videos online, showcasing users experience, how startups gain a direct benefit from SIEUGREEN etc., the video-sharing website of YouTube has been chosen. Since the accounts of Google and YouTube connect to each other, on the 31st of January a Google and YouTube (at the same time) account has been created. On the 27th of June 2018 the YouTube account is active but has not still content to share. That is the case since the project is now starting to develop and the video content will be created later on the duration of SIEUGREEN.

Chinese Social Media

As it has been stated in the previous paragraphs, the current situation of Social Media in mainland China is very different compared to the EU. As of May 2018, more than 8,000 domain names are blocked in mainland China under the country's Internet censorship policy ("*GreatFire.org - Bringing Transparency To The Great Firewall Of China*". Archived from the original on 18 May 2018. Retrieved 19 May 2018) which prevents users from accessing proscribed websites in the country. In these banned Social Media are included all the aforementioned, used in the context of SiEUGreen project, but LinkedIn. As a result, there is the need for a Chinese partner to create content in Chinese social media in correspondence to the European ones. This need is driven both from the necessity for the use of the Chinese language and the actual knowledge of Chinese social media themselves. Bellow there is a table presenting indicatively the 10 most popular Chinese social media websites in correspondence to the EU ones.

Table 13: The 10 Most Popular Social Media Sites in China

1. WeChat:	All-in-on Social Media in China
2. Sina Weibo:	Twitter of China
3. Tencent QQ:	Popular Instant Messaging App
4. Toudou Youku:	YouTube of China
5. Baidu Tieba:	A Search Engine Forum
6. Douban:	Lifestyle Discussion Platform
7. Zhihu:	The Quora of China
8. Meituan-Dianping:	The Chinese Versions of Yelp
9. Momo:	Tinder of China
10. Meipai:	Chinese Instagram for Video

The chosen partner from China will collaborate, principally with 6-Emetris and all other partners of the project for the smooth management of the Chinese social media. The Chinese representative will increase the presence, to attract candidates to interact with the project and to develop and promote all the actions during the whole period of the project. Chinese Social Media Platforms will be utilized to reach both special stakeholder groups but also the broader society. Until, the 27th of June 2018 the Chinese partners have not finalized their legal (managerial) procedures and consequently the relevant processes are delayed.

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Annex III - Consent form for external events

A table that will be used as indicative consent form to be signed in the case of external events can be found below. Each project partner can use and adapt it according to each case.

“By entering my email address below, I agree to its use for sending information on the SiEUGreen project activities and key outcomes by the SiEUGreen consortium:”

First Name	Last Name	Organization	Position	Email address	Signature	I agree for the use of my email for sending information regarding the SiEUGreen project (Yes/ No)

Annex IV - List of Public Deliverables

ID	Deliverable Title	WP	LP	Type	Due Month
D1.1	Maps of quantitative and qualitative data for each of the showcase locations	WP1	5-NORDREGIO	Report	6
D1.2	Baseline study including key indicators and development of a typology	WP1	5-NORDREGIO	Report	12
1.3	Whitepaper with best practices	WP1	5-NORDREGIO	Report	46
1.4	Guidelines for a new interactive impact assessment approaches	WP1	5-NORDREGIO	Report	36
1.5	Engagement strategy	WP1	5-NORDREGIO	Websites, patents filling etc.	42
2.1	Green Technology (T1) ready	WP2	2-NIBIO	Other	16
2.2	Evaluation of crop techniques	WP2	2-NIBIO	Report	16
2.3	Blue Technology (T2) Ready 1	WP2	1-NMBU	Report	16
2.4	Blue Technology (T2) Ready 2	WP2	1-NMBU	Report	16
2.5	Recommendation document for nutrient and energy supply in each showcase	WP2	2-NIBIO	Report	45
2.6	Social awareness and acceptance report	WP2	2-NIBIO	Report	45
3.1	Requirement plans for each of the showcase locations	WP3	2-NIBIO	Websites, patents filling etc.	12
3.2	Common implementation framework	WP3	8-VILABS	Report	14
3.3	Mid-term Showcase deployment report	WP3	8-VILABS	Report	30
3.4	Final Showcase deployment report	WP3	8-VILABS	Report	45
3.5	City benchmarking	WP3	8-VILABS	Report	48
3.6	COMMURBAN software delivery	WP3	4-CREVIS	Other	46
4.2	Transnational board meeting report and issue of white paper	WP4	2-NIBIO	Other	36
5.1	Market analysis 1	WP5	4-CREVIS	Websites, patents filling etc.	8
5.2	Market analysis 2	WP5	4-CREVIS	Websites, patents filling etc.	21
5.3	Market analysis 3	WP5	4-CREVIS	Websites, patents filling etc.	36

ID	Deliverable Title	WP	LP	Type	Due Month
5.4	Sustainability and Exploitation Plan	WP5	4-CREVIS	Websites, patents filling etc.	30
5.5	Business plan	WP5	4-CREVIS	Websites, patents filling etc.	46
5.6	Handbook for SiEUGreen solutions replication	WP5	4-CREVIS	Websites, patents filling etc.	40
5.7	Establishment of Sustainability Working Group	WP5	4-CREVIS	Other	18
6.1	Dissemination plan	WP6	6-EMETRIS	Report	6
6.2	Project website	WP6	9-OKYS LTD	Websites, patents filling etc.	10
6.3	Promotional material	WP6	6-EMETRIS	Other	12
6.4	Policy recommendations	WP6	6-EMETRIS	Report	48
7.1	Quality Assurance - Risk Management plan	WP7	1-NMBU	Report	3
7.2	Data management and RRI plan	WP7	1-NMBU	ORDP	6

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Annex V - SiEUGreen Logos

SiEUGreen

Sino-European innovative green
and smart cities

Figure 6: SiEUGreen Logo of the project

SiEU Green

Sino-European innovative green
and smart cities

Figure 7: SiEUGreen Logo of the project (b/w)

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 774233

Co-funded by the Horizon 2020 programme
of the European Union

Co-funded by the Chinese Ministry
of Science and Technology